
The relationships between electronic structure and human A₁ adenosine receptor binding affinity in a series of triazolopyridine derivatives

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Abstract Some triazolopyridine derivatives present a good binding affinity for the human adenosine A₁ receptor. In this paper we present the results of the examination of the relationships between the electronic structure of these molecules and the A₁ receptor binding affinity. The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method was employed. A statistically significant equation, involving four local atomic reactivity indices, was obtained. Starting from the QSAR results we built the 2D-pharmacophore including the suggested interactions with the binding site. On the basis of the results we suggest the test of two modifications of the actual structures. One involves the breakdown of the π structure by inserting a methylene group and the other to use simultaneously the same substituents on atoms 2 and 6 of a phenyl ring.

Keywords KPG method, QSAR, adenosine receptors, A₁ receptor, triazolopyridine derivatives, ligand-site interactions, molecular interactions

Introduction

Adenosine receptors (ARs) are a family of G protein-coupled receptors. There are four subtypes, named A₁, A_{2A}, A_{2B} and A₃. All are activated by extracellular adenosine. They are extensively distributed in almost all human body tissues and organs. A₁ and A₃ receptors inhibit adenylyl cyclase, through Gi/o proteins, while A_{2A} and A_{2B} receptors stimulate it through Gs proteins. ARs play a central role in a broad range of physiological processes, including vasodilation, pain, inflammation, sleep regulation, angiogenesis and modulation of the immune system [1-3].

For these reasons, ARs are potential targets in a variety of illnesses, such as sleep disorders, cancer and dementia. A large number of experimental and theoretical studies have been carried out with the aim to obtain information about the interaction of new molecules with ARs receptors with the purpose of finding more powerful ligands to modulate the adenosine receptors [4-25]. Recently, a group of 7-amino-2-aryl/hetero-aryl-5-oxo-5,8-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-a]pyridine-6-carbonitriles (hereafter triazolopyridine derivatives) were synthesized and their binding affinity toward ARs was experimentally measured [8].

We present here the results of the application of the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) QSAR method to the study of the relationships between the human A₁ adenosine receptor binding affinity (hA₁) and the electronic structure of the above mentioned molecules. This work also serves as a test of the power of the KPG method to account for these molecular systems and biological activities.

Methods, Models and Calculations

Method

The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) QSAR method has been reviewed with detail in various publications [26-35]. It consists in a linear equation relating the logarithm of a biological activity (BA, measured *in vivo* or *in vitro*) with a group of local atomic reactivity indices (LARIs) of a collection of atoms of the molecule:

$$\log(\text{BA}) = a + f(\text{LARIs}) \quad (1)$$

where a is a constant. The LARIs are associated with atom-atom electrostatic interactions, electron donor and acceptor properties, maximum charge that an atom may receive, etc. If we have a group of N molecules we have to solve a system of N linear equations. On the other hand, each atom is described by a set of twenty LARIs (this is a minimal set that can be enlarged). Logics dictates that in this linear system of equations any atom appearing in one equation must appear in all others (it is not necessary that all be the same element). The set of these atoms is called the common skeleton and for a group of molecules it can be of different sizes (i.e., it can be composed by different number of atoms). Let us consider a common skeleton of 10 atoms. We shall need the experimental BAs of about 200 molecules to solve this system! We do not know a paper or series of papers with such information. A first approach to diminish the number of LARIs to be used is by analyzing the numerical values and discarding the ones with a standard deviation closed to zero (a rigorous definition of 'close to zero' is needed). The second approach is to focus our attention on those reactivity indices whose variation in their numerical values explains the variation in biological activity. In this case, Eq. 1 is written as:

$$\Delta \log(\text{BA}) = a + f(\Delta \text{LARIs}) \quad (2)$$

In this case we can employ Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) to find these indices. The advantages are that we can use many more LARIs than molecules and enlarge the common skeleton if necessary. The shortcoming is that only some LARIs will appear in the statistically significant equation obtained. The selection of the common skeleton should ensure that it accounts for practically all the interactions leading to the appearance of the biological activity. The applications of KPG method to different molecules and biological activities produced very good results [35-47].

Selection of molecules and biological activities

The molecules are a group of triazolopyridine derivatives selected from a recent study [8]. Their general formula and hA_1 receptor affinity are displayed, respectively, in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1: General formulas of triazolopyridine derivatives

Table 1: Molecules and hA_1 binding affinity

Mol.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	log(K _i)
1	H	H	H	H	-1.12
2	H	H	OH	H	-0.94
3	H	H	CH ₃	H	-0.28
4	H	H	NH(CH ₃) ₂	H	0.74
5	OCH ₃	H	H	H	0.76
6	H	H	OCH ₃	H	0.63
7	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	0.91
8	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	0

9	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	-0.06
10	H	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	0.24
11	H	NO ₂	H	H	0.39
12	H	H	NO ₂	H	0.86
13	H	H	F	H	-0.38
14	Cl	H	H	H	-0.53
15	H	H	Cl	H	-0.08
16	Cl	H	Cl	H	-0.13
17	H	H	Br	H	-0.23
18	H	H	H	H	-0.07

Calculations

The electronic structure was calculated within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level with full geometry optimization [48]. The Gaussian 09 software was used. All the data to calculate the numerical values for the local atomic reactivity indices was obtained from the Gaussian results with the D-Cent-QSAR software [49]. All electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01 e were considered as being zero. Negative electron populations coming from Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected as usual [50]. For LMRA, a matrix containing the dependent variable (the binding affinity) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton as independent variables was built. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [51]. The common skeleton is shown in Fig. 2. Numbers 22 to 25 design hydrogen atoms or the atom directly attached to the ring in the case of other substituents.

Figure 2: Common skeleton numbering of triazolopyridine derivatives

Results

The best equation obtained was:

$$\Delta \log(K_i) = 4.14 - 143.37 \Delta F_{15}(\text{HOMO})^* + 0.012 \Delta S_{16}^N(\text{LUMO} + 2)^* - 2.20 \Delta F_{22}(\text{HOMO} - 2)^* + 1.40 \Delta F_{17}(\text{LUMO} + 1)^* \quad (3)$$

with $n=18$, $R=0.96$, $R^2=0.92$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.90$, $F(4,13)=39.49$ ($p < 0.000001$) and $SD=0.19$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $F_{15}(\text{HOMO})^*$ is the Fukui index (the electron population) of the highest occupied MO localized on atom 15, $S_{16}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty MO localized on atom 16, $F_{22}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index (the electron population) of the third highest occupied MO localized on atom 22 and $F_{17}(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$ is the Fukui index (the electron population) of the second lowest empty MO localized on atom 17. Tables 2 and 3 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 3. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 3 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(K_i)$.

Table 2: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 3

	Beta	t(13)	p-level
F ₁₅ (HOMO)*	-0.97	-10.40	<0.0000001
S ₁₆ ^N (LUMO+2)*	0.52	6.83	<0.00001
F ₂₂ (HOMO-2)*	-0.38	-4.58	<0.0005
F ₁₇ (LUMO+1)*	0.28	3.22	<0.007

Table 3: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 3

	F ₁₅ (HOMO)*	S ₁₆ ^N (LUMO+2)*	F ₂₂ (HOMO-2)*
F ₁₅ (HOMO)*	1.00		
S ₁₆ ^N (LUMO+2)*	0.00	1.00	
F ₂₂ (HOMO-2)*	0.13	0.01	1.00
F ₁₇ (LUMO+1)*	0.24	0.00	0.02

Figure 3: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(K_i)$ values (Eq. 3). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 3 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 90% of the variation of $\log(K_i)$. Figure 3, spanning about 1.9 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed versus calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 4 shows the local MO structure of atoms 15, 16, 17 and 22 (see Fig. 2). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)*-(LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 4: Local molecular orbitals of atoms 15, 16, 17 and 22

Mol.	Atom 15	Atom 16	Atom 17	Atom 22
1 (65)	61π62π65π- 66π68π 69π	61π63π65π- 67π68π69π	60σ64π65π- 66π67π68π	50σ55σ57σ- 75σ76σ79σ
2 (69)	65π66σ69π- 70π72π73π	65π67π69π- 71π72π73π	67π68π69π- 70π71π73π	56σ60σ61σ- 81σ83σ84σ
3 (69)	65π66σ69π-	65π67π69π-	64σ68π69π-	59σ61σ62σ-

	70π72π73π	71π72π73π	70π71π72π	80σ81σ83σ
4 (77)	72σ73σ77π-	71π74π77π-	75π76π77π-	63σ68σ69σ-
	78π79π80π	79π80π81π	78π79π80π	85σ89σ90σ
5 (73)	70σ72π73π-	71π72π73π-	68σ72π73π-	70σ72π73π-
	74π76π77 π	75π76π77π	74π75π76π	75π77π83σ
6 (73)	69π70σ73π-	67π71π73π-	71π72π73π-	59σ61σ66σ-
	74π75π76π	75π76π77π	74π75π77π	83σ85σ87σ
7 (81)	77π78σ81π-	75π80π81π-	76σ80π81π-	66σ70σ72σ-
	82π83π84π	83π84π85π	82π83π84π	91σ93σ94σ
8 (81)	77π78σ81π-	77π79π81π-	74π80π81π-	78σ80π81π-
	82π83π84π	83π84π85π	83π85π93σ	83π85π91σ
9 (77)	73π74σ76π-	75π76π77π-	70σ76π77π-	74σ76π77π-
	78π80π83π	79π80π81π	78π79π80π	79π81π100π
10 (85)	80σ81σ85π-	82π84π85π-	82π84π85π-	68σ71σ77σ-
	86π87π88π	87π88π90π	86π87π88π	93σ96σ98σ
11 (76)	70π72σ76π-	70π75π76π-	74π75π76π-	57σ60σ62σ-
	78π79π80π	77π78π79π	77π78π79π	87σ90σ91σ
12 (76)	69π72σ76π-	69π75π76π-	74π75π76π-	57σ60σ63σ-
	78π79π80π	77π78π80π	77π79π80π	87σ88σ90σ
13 (69)	65π66σ69π-	65π68π69π-	64σ67π69π-	54σ56σ60σ-
	70π72π73π	71π72π73π	70π71π73π	79σ80σ82σ
14 (73)	69σ70σ73π-	71π72π73π-	70σ72π73π-	70σ72π73π-
	74π75π76π	75π76π77π	74π75π77π	75π77π81σ
15 (73)	69π70σ73π-	69π72π73π-	68σ71π73π-	59σ61σ66σ-
	74π76π77π	75π76π77π	74π75π77π	79σ86σ87σ
16 (81)	77σ78σ81π-	77σ79π81π-	79π80π81π-	79π80π81π-
	82π83π84π	82π83π84π	82π83π84π	83π85π86σ
17 (82)	78π79σ82π-	75π81π82π-	78π80π82π-	64σ69σ70σ-
	83π85π86π	83π84π85π	83π84π86π	87σ94σ96σ
18 (65)	62σ64σ65π-	63π64σ65π-	63π64σ65π-	49σ53σ64σ-
	66π67π68π	66π67π68π	66π67π68π	75σ76σ78σ

Discussion

When a local atomic reactivity index of an inner occupied MO (i.e., HOMO-1 and/or HOMO-2) or of a higher vacant MO (LUMO+1 and/or LUMO+2) appears in any equation, this means that the remaining of the upper occupied MOs (for example, if HOMO-2 appears, upper means HOMO-1 and HOMO) or the remaining of the empty MOs (for example, if LUMO+1 appears, lower means the LUMO) also contribute to the drug-receptor interaction. Their absence in the equation only means that the variation of their numerical values does not account for the variation of the numerical value of the biological property. Table 2 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 3 is $F_{15}(\text{HOMO})^* \gg S_{16}^{\text{N}}(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > F_{22}(\text{HOMO}-2)^* > F_{17}(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$. The analysis of this equation using the suggestions previously published shows that a high hA_1 binding affinity is associated with high numerical values for $F_{15}(\text{HOMO})^*$ and $F_{22}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$, and with small numerical values for $S_{16}^{\text{N}}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and $F_{17}(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$.

Atom 15 is a nitrogen atom in ring B (Fig. 2). Its local HOMO* coincides with the molecular HOMO in all but one cases (where the local HOMO* coincides with the molecular (HOMO-1), see Table 4) and is of π nature. As a high electron population is associated with a high binding affinity, it is theoretically possible to raise its numerical value by localizing the molecular HOMO only on this atom (with an electron population of 2)³⁴. But if we were able to detect other atoms in which the local HOMO* coincides with the molecular HOMO and high values of electron population are also essential for high affinity, then we need to find the appropriate substitutions to achieve this objective. Figure 4 shows the HOMO of molecule 1.

Figure 4: Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital of molecule 1

We can see that the whole ring B can be interacting with an aromatic ring or an aromatic residue through π - π interactions [35]. This because the local HOMO* of all atoms composing this ring coincides with the molecular HOMO.

Atom 16 is a carbon atom of ring C connected to ring B (Fig. 2). Table 4 shows that the three highest occupied local MOs and the three lowest empty MOs are of π nature. Small numerical values for $S_{16}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ are associated with high binding affinity. Remembering that any nucleophilic superdelocalizability corresponds to an electron population of a molecular orbital divided by the energy of this molecular orbital, a small value will be obtained mainly by raising the MO energy [34]. Physically this means that this MO will be less prone to accept electrons. On the other hand, in only four cases the local LUMO* coincides with the molecular LUMO while in all cases the local HOMO* coincides with the molecular LUMO. Figure 4 shows that the HOMO is localized on atom 16. All this data reinforces the idea that atom 16 appears to participate in a π - π interaction [35].

Atom 22 can be a hydrogen atom or the atom directly bonded to atom 17 in the case of polyatomic substituents (Fig. 2). In this occasion we are in presence of H, OH, OMe and Cl substituents. High numerical values of $F_{22}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ are associated with high affinity. In the case of H atoms the nature of the three highest occupied local MOs is $\sigma\sigma\sigma$ (Table 4). Also $(\text{HOMO})_{22}^*$ coincides with molecular MOs that are very far from the molecular HOMO. This suggests that in this case we are in presence of atoms with a very low electron donating capacity that could participate in a carbon hydrogen bond interaction [35]. Figure 5 shows $(\text{HOMO}-2)_{22}^*$ of molecule 1 (for molecule 1 this is MO 50 and HOMO is MO 65).

Figure 5: $(\text{HOMO}-2)_{22}^*$ of atom 22 in molecule 1 (MO 50)

In the case of OH and OMe substituents the nature of the three highest occupied local MOs of the oxygen atoms is $\sigma\pi\pi$ (Table 4). Local HOMO_{22}^* and local $(\text{HOMO}-1)_{22}^*$ match their molecular equivalents, HOMO and (HOMO-1). In the case of $(\text{HOMO}-2)_{22}^*$ we may suggest a carbon hydrogen bond interaction [35]. For HOMO_{22}^* and $(\text{HOMO}-1)_{22}^*$, both of π nature, we may suggest a participation in a π - π interaction [35]. In this last case the oxygen atoms

could be part of a more extended aromatic system covering ring C (Fig. 2). Figure 6 shows the (HOMO-3) σ MO of molecule 5. For atom 22 this corresponds to $(\text{HOMO-2})_{22}^*$.

Figure 6: $(\text{HOMO-2})_{22}^*$ of atom 22 in molecule 5 (also (HOMO-3) of molecule 5, MO 70)

In the case of the chlorine substituent the nature of the three highest occupied local MOs is $\sigma\pi\pi$ or $\pi\pi\pi$ (Table 4). Using the same reasoning above, we can suggest that chlorine atoms can be involved in π - π (as part of an extended aromatic system covering ring C), halogen and/or weak alkyl interactions [35]. Figure 7 shows $(\text{HOMO-2})_{22}^*$ of molecule 16.

Figure 7: $(\text{HOMO-2})_{22}^*$ of atom 22 in molecule 1 (also HOMO-2 of molecule 16)

Atom 17 is a carbon atom in ring C (Fig. 2). Note that atom 22 is bonded to this atom. Small numerical values for $F_{17}(\text{LUMO+1})^*$ are associated with high binding affinity. The nature of local LUMO_{17}^* and $(\text{LUMO+1})_{17}^*$ is $\pi\pi$ in all molecules (Table 4). Also, in all but two molecules these local MOs coincide with the molecular LUMO and (LUMO+1). In the remaining cases local LUMO_{17}^* and $(\text{LUMO+1})_{17}^*$ coincide with the molecular LUMO and (LUMO+2) in one molecule and with the molecular (LUMO+1) and (LUMO+3) in the other. The best way to proceed in this case is by suppressing the localization of low energy empty MOs on this atom [34]. This will reduce its electron-accepting capacity. Considering that $(\text{HOMO})_{17}^*$ coincides with the molecular HOMO and that in all cases it has a π nature we suggest that atom 17 is involved in a π - π interaction [35]. This suggestion is consistent with one of the suggestions made for atom 22. The corresponding 2D partial pharmacophore is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Partial 2D pharmacophore

The inspection of figures 2 and 8 suggests that it would be convenient to test some new variations of the molecular structure of these systems. The first would be to test the condition that atoms 17 and 22 have the same substituents. The second would be to break the pi system and give ring C greater conformational flexibility. This is done by inserting a CH₂ group between rings B and C.

In summary, we have obtained a statistically significant relationship between the variation of the human A₁ adenosine receptor binding affinity and the variation of the numerical values of some local atomic reactivity indices. These results allowed us to propose the testing of new molecular structures.

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